

PRACTICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS THROUGH EDUCATIONAL PODCASTS

Saidvalieva Dilafruz Ravshanovna

Teacher in Foreign languages department in Tashkent University of Information Technologies
named after Muhammad al – Khwarizmi in Tashkent, Uzbekistan,

e-mail: dilravshanovna@icloud.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10837700>

Abstract. *This academic paper aims to investigate the potential advantages of integrating podcasts into English as a Second Language (ESL) teaching in higher educational institutions. The study reviews current research on the use of podcasts as a technological tool to enhance language learning, particularly in the context of English language acquisition. The paper discusses the impact of podcasts on language proficiency and student motivation, and provides recommendations for educators seeking to incorporate podcasts into their ESL teaching practices.*

Keywords: *podcast, educational podcast categorization, listening skills, speaking skills, language acquisition.*

Аннотация. *Целью данной научной статьи является исследование потенциальных преимуществ интеграции подкастов в преподавание английского как второго языка (ESL) в высших учебных заведениях. В исследовании рассматриваются текущие исследования по использованию подкастов в качестве технологического инструмента для улучшения изучения языка, особенно в контексте изучения английского языка. В документе обсуждается влияние подкастов на знание языка и мотивацию учащихся, а также приводятся рекомендации для преподавателей, стремящихся включить подкасты в свою практику преподавания английского как иностранного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *подкаст, категоризация образовательных подкастов, навыки аудир*

Annotasiya. *Ushbu ilmiy maqola oliy o'quv yurtlarida podkastlarni ingliz tiliga ikkinchi til (ESL) sifatida o'qitishning potentsial afzalliklarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Ayniqsa, ingliz tilini o'zlashtirish kontekstida til o'rganishni yaxshilash uchun texnologik vosita sifatida podkastlardan foydalanish bo'yicha joriy tadqiqotlarni ko'rib chiqadi. Maqolada podkastlarning tilni bilish darajasi va talabalar motivatsiyasiga ta'siri muhokama qilinadi va podkastlarni ESL o'qitish amaliyotiga qo'shishga intilayotgan o'qituvchilar uchun tavsiyalar berilgan.*

Калит so'zlar: *podkast, ta'lim podkastlari toifalari, tinglash qobiliyatlari, nutq qobiliyatlari, tilni o'zlashtirish. ования, навыки говорения, овладение языком.*

Modern teachers actively and in detail master the possibilities of working with Internet technologies in the learning process. With the advent of social services Web 2.0. specialists in the field of lingua didactics and methods of teaching foreign languages fully support the use of information and communication technologies (ICT). Namely: conferences and webinars are being organized; didactic materials are created with links to Internet resources and tasks that involve working with Internet material; programs are written for teaching a foreign language.

Web 2.0 services, or social services, are web-based software that supports group interactions. These include search engines, knowledge maps, social networks, blogs, services for storing bookmarks, video and photo materials, etc. According to the point of view of P. V. Sysoev, “Podcast social service is a type of social service in Web 2.0, allowing listening, creating and distributing audio and video recordings” [3].

The concept of "podcast" comes from the English word podcasting, which became famous thanks to the widespread use of Apple portable media players, the founder of which is Steve Jobs. The word podcasting itself arose by combining two words - "iPod" and "broadcasting" (English - radio and television broadcasting; broadcast) and is a special format of audio and video broadcasts produced on the World Wide Web [2].

According to the Macmillan dictionary [4], a podcast is a multimedia file that can be downloaded from the Internet and listened to on audio and video players.

E.Yu. Malushko gives the following definition of a podcast: “A podcast is an audio or video file that is distributed free of charge over the Internet for mass listening or viewing” [1].

P.V. Sysoev defines a podcast as "an audio or video recording made by any person and available for listening or viewing on the World Wide Web" [2]. According to this definition, it should be concluded that the authorship of a podcast can belong to any person.

Based on the considered definitions, it is necessary to note the most general concept of a podcast, which was developed by L.I. Agafonova and Zh. S. Anikina. The authors give the following definition of podcast technology - "an audio or video file distributed on the Internet for listening on a personal computer or mobile devices" [1].

It is believed that the word "podcasting" was coined by the well-known American VJ, former MTV host Adam Curry in 2004. Actually, then it was included in the New Oxford American Dictionary (Oxford Dictionary), and in 2005 it became the “Word of the Year”. In 2004, after the appearance of the word, the Google search engine for a podcast query gave first 24 results, then 526, three days later - 2750 and this number doubled every day. As a result, Adam Curry can rightly be called the founding father of podcasting.

The didactic potential of podcasting is based on the basic technical and didactic characteristics of this Internet technology:

1. Authenticity. Podcasts are authentic material that is intended to be listened to at different stages of language learning, so podcasts can greatly enrich and diversify an English lesson. A huge number of podcasts act as didactic material with manuscripts and accompanying texts, notes on the degree of difficulty and didactic recommendations, as well as assignments for the proposed passage and can be applied at different levels of learning a foreign language. Obviously, the process of mastering a foreign language becomes more entertaining, motivated and effective when students find themselves in an authentic situation [8].

2. Relevance. Podcasting technology offers a wide opportunity for users to regularly update their archive with new audio and video materials from the Internet. By subscribing to receive podcasts, users can have daily audio and video files on their PC with up-to-date information about various areas of life, which can be used in English classes or outside of it.

3. Competence in the field of media. The technical conditions for using podcasts are absolutely simple. The teacher only needs to download the required podcast in the required format on a PC or other media. This skill is the key to a huge motivational potential. When we, together with students, begin to explore a new learning tool and give them the opportunity to understand their technical savvy, the attractiveness of the tool and the ability to handle technical innovations motivates and pushes students to both independent and group work [8].

4. Autonomy. Autonomy allows functioning according to learning needs, learning pace and level of learning, as it is one of the main advantages of the Internet as a learning platform. If students themselves determine the conditions of their learning in terms of the principles of

autonomous learning, the autonomous environment as a factor in the success of learning both surpasses the traditional communicative lesson and competes with it [6].

5. Multichannel perception. The podcast service regularly offers content for students. These materials are built on a combination of sound, photo or video pictures, as well as text materials. The teacher has ample opportunities to use multi-channel learning materials in one lesson, i.e. use different organs of perception at the same time. This, in turn, expands the receptive capabilities of students, acts as an important key to understanding information in English, and motivates for oral and written statements on the topic [7].

6. The mobility of the technical means used makes it possible to access the podcast materials both in the classroom and outside the educational institution at any time. In this case, we can talk about expanding the learning environment. Access to podcasts outside of the classroom provides a chance to learn in your spare time and the opportunity to work with individual receptive skills, tailor understanding of a complex audio passage to your personal perceptual characteristics. This, in turn, allows you to remove the label of an unpleasant obligation or task of increased complexity from listening [8].

7. Multifunctionality. Due to the versatility of the podcasting system, it can be used to develop several types of speech activity. Along with classical listening, the improvement of oral and written speech skills will be relevant. Along with this, podcasts provide knowledge about the diversity of both the language and the culture of the language being studied in a convenient environment for listeners [7].

8. Productivity. The use of reproduced materials is one of the aspects of working with podcasts in the classroom. Creating and further distributing your own podcasts is another. In terms of productivity, the podcasting system is a significant impetus for learning a foreign language in terms of an activity approach. By creating and publishing audio or video materials online, students work with promising information technology in a real situation [4].

9. Interactivity. At the current stage of the development of the Internet, interactivity seems to be the main idea of the Web 2.0 concept, according to which not only consumption is significant, when users only listen, read or view information, but also actively interact with other people on the Internet.

The integration of podcasting into teaching a foreign language with its wide potential for cooperative interaction has the best effect on the interactivity of the educational process [7].

Thus, educational podcasts dedicated to the study of foreign languages make it possible to solve a number of methodological problems, including the formation of auditory skills and the ability to understand foreign speech by ear, the formation and improvement of auditory pronunciation skills, the expansion and enrichment of the lexical dictionary, the formation and improvement of grammatical skills, development of speaking and writing skills.

Significant didactic possibilities of podcasts and their effectiveness in teaching English can be identified through experimental work.

Today, the podcasting system is not limited to amateur radio. Despite the simplicity of creating a podcast, on podcasting portals it is possible to find official podcasts of on-air radio, television channels, and large companies. For example, the latest news releases, a story about promotions or new service opportunities.

Podcasts are new, fashionable, modern, and, most importantly, convenient.

To date, you can count a fairly large number of podcasts that differ from each other in certain ways. Before turning to the social services of podcasts intended for teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to place a small emphasis on their general classification given by L.I. Agafonova and Zh.S. Anikina, which covers all aspects of the social server and identifies six types of podcasts [3]:

1. Depending on the technical platform, the authors distinguish between *standalone* (created using offline software) and *integrated* (created within a specific site) podcasts;
 2. By type of multimedia, podcasts are divided into *audio* and *video podcasts*.
 3. According to the number of authors, they can be *individual* and *collective*;
 4. By genre, podcasts are *educational, entertaining and socio-political*.
- G. Stanley proposes to distinguish between podcasts in terms of their authorship:

- *Authentic Podcasts (authentic podcasts)*

Files with recording of native speakers. Among them are podcasts that are not recorded for linguistic purposes, but which can serve as a rich resource for listening and podcasts created as educational materials, especially for foreign language learners.

- *Podcasts created by teachers (teacher podcasts)*

Podcasts are recorded by educators most often for their own use and are made to give students access to material that is not available anywhere else.

- *Student podcasts (student podcasts)*

Podcasts recorded by students themselves, often with the help of a teacher. Students can listen to these samples to get acquainted with other cultures and life of students in different countries.

- *Methodical (educator podcasts)*. Podcasts for professional development of teachers, self-development and exchange of methodological information.

Yu.P. Agel notes that there are different types of podcasts related to the study of foreign languages, which can be divided depending on the goal set for the teacher:

- podcasts for working with lexical material, where the author explains the meaning of a word, phrase or idiom and illustrates them with examples of the functioning of the considered lexical unit in the language;
- podcasts aimed at developing listening skills and including listening tasks;
- podcasts designed to conduct a whole lesson in a foreign language [6].

The above points, from the point of view of teaching methods, make the use of the Internet in the system of teaching English relevant and provide by far the most effective development of all types of speech activity, and listening in particular. Moreover, the use of Internet technologies and podcasts in teaching English shows the mobility of the modern education system, its adaptive nature, i.e. timely adaptation to innovative technologies.

Thus, the new information technology "podcasting" has great potential both in the field of education in general and for teaching English as a foreign language in particular. The ability to easily download podcasts to mp3 players and iPods makes the process of learning English continuous, and the learning itself is available not only in the classroom, but also in any other environment. The availability of audio recording software makes it easy to create podcasts. The possibility of placing them on the Web - motivates to learn English. In addition, working with podcasts provides students with the opportunity to gain experience with lexical and grammatical

material. With this technology, teaching English becomes student-centered. Teachers, in turn, with the help of podcast technology can achieve better results in teaching listening skills compared to traditional methods.

REFERENCES

1. Brown H. D. Principles of language learning and teaching. N.Y.: Longman, 2000.
2. Brown H. D. Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy. N.Y.: Longman, 2001.
3. Corbeil J. C. The Macmillan Visual Dictionary. M: , 1992.
4. Fryer W. A. Podcasting as disruptive trans mediation / W.A. Fryer // eLearn2005: World Conference on eLearning in Corporate, Government, Healthcare, & Higher Education. 2005.
5. Lee M. J. W. Teaching and Learning in the Web 2.0 Era: Empowering Students Through Learner-generated Content / M.J.W. Lee, C. McLoughlin // International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning. 2007. Vol. 4. №3. P. 588-595.
6. Prensky M. Digital Natives, Digital Immigrants / M. Prensky // On the Horizon. Vol. 9. № 5. October 2001. P. 1-6.
7. Robb T. N. Podcasting for ELT – What, Why and How? 2007 // Kyoto Sangyo University Vol. 20. №5. P. 546-587
8. Roberts M. Adventures in podcasting // Political Science and Politics. 2008.
9. Stanley G. Podcasting for ELT / G. Stanley. Barcelona: British Council, 2005. 100 p.
10. Saidvalieva, D. (2023). Choosing an Effective Podcasting Service for Learning English Language. Bulletin of Science and Practice, 9(5), 588-591. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/90/79>
11. Saidvalieva, D. (2021). Teaching Methods of English for Specific Purposes. Bulletin of Science and Practice, 7(6), 481-485. <https://doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/67/62>